

ELEVATED TEMPERATURE TENSILE RESPONSE OF ALUMINUM-THERMOPLASTIC LAMINA HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

in this study, hybrid composites were fabricated by adhesively bonding lamina of 2024-T3 or 2024-T81 monolithic aluminum alloy to either polyether etherketone (PEEK)/AS4 graphite or J2/Kevlar® 49 continuous, unidirectional fiber reinforced composite cores. AF163-2U and AF191-M structural film adhesives manufactured by 3M were utilized in the adhesive bonding process. The hybrids were tested for longitudinal and transverse tensile properties at ambient and elevated temperatures up to 225 °C. The ambient temperature tensile strength of longitudinal PEEK/AS4 graphite-aluminum composites ranged from 655-725 MPa, while transverse specimens recorded strengths of 300-315 MPa. Longitudinal and transverse J2/Kevlar® 49-aluminum hybrids displayed strengths of 575-600 MPa and 300-325 MPa respectively. The longitudinal hybrid composites retained a minimum of 75% of their ambient temperature tensile strength and modulus at temperatures up to 225 °C. SEM micrographs of fractured surfaces indicated fiber pullout and interfacial debonding were the two dominant failure modes in the elevated temperature range.

INTRODUCTION

Lamina hybrid composites refer to structural laminates consisting of a fiber reinforced polymer matrix composite core adhesively bonded to thin isotropic outer metallic layers. Hybrid composites of this type are unique since the proper choice of the fiber system enables the design engineer to tailor the resultant properties of the hybrid. For example, the incorporation of a graphite fiber composite core would result in higher specific strength and stiffness, while glass fiber systems would be more suitable for damage tolerant, low cost applications.

Collaborative efforts between Delft University and Fokker Aircraft during the 1980s resulted in the creation of ARALL® laminates; structural materials consisting of isotropic aluminum alloy sheets adhesively bonded by an aramid fiber reinforced epoxy adhesive [1-3]. The material has been subsequently developed by Alcoa and 3M [4-5]. The fiber reinforcement greatly enhances the fatigue response and specific properties of aluminum, while the aluminum imparts increased transverse

properties and corrosion resistance to the hybrid composites. In this study, thermoplastic polymer composites were utilized in place of ARALL®'s thermoset composite core. The utilization of fiber reinforced thermoplastic resins offers many unique advantages—such as improved toughness and damage tolerance, increased moisture and solvent resistance and improved repairability—as compared with the aramid-epoxy material currently used in the manufacture of ARALL® laminates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Lamina hybrid composites were fabricated by adhesively bonding PEEK/AS4 graphite and J2/Kevlar® 49 composite cores to 0.31mm thick 2024-T3 and 2024-T81 aluminum sheets with 0.13mm thick AF-163-2U and AF-191-M structural film adhesives. The fiber reinforced composite cores were fabricated by compression molding either two PEEK/AS4 graphite or four J2/Kevlar® 49 unidirectional prepreg layers (each layer 0.13 mm thick) in a 254mm x 127mm closed steel mold. The mold was placed in a Machine Technologies hot platen press and heated under a contact pressure of 0.07 MPa. Once the thermoplastic's processing temperature (i.e. 300 °C for J2/Kevlar® 49 and 365 °C for PEEK/AS4 graphite) was reached, an external pressure of 1.75 MPa was applied to the mold. After 20 minutes, the mold was allowed to cool under pressure. When a cooling temperature of 150 °C was reached, the composite cores were removed from the mold.

In all cases, phosphoric acid anodized and primed aluminum sheets were used to fabricate the hybrid composites. In an effort to promote adhesive bonding between the epoxy and the thermoplastic, a surface treatment procedure was utilized to prepare the composite cores. The thermoplastic cores were first wiped clean with acetone in order to remove surface contaminants and entrapped mold release. Next, the specimens were abraded with 240 grit abrasive paper and etched in a chromic-sulfuric acid solution for 8 minutes (J2/Kevlar® 49) and 45 minutes (PEEK/AS4 graphite) at 80 °C.

The aluminum sheets, the reinforced thermoplastic core and the film adhesive were aligned within the 254 mm by 127 mm mold. The mold was inserted into the laminating press and heated to 120 °C (AF-163-2U) and 175 °C (AF-191-M) at a rate of 5 °C/minute. The adhesive was cured at these temperatures for 1 hour at a pressure of 0.35 MPa. The mold was then cooled to room temperature and the finished laminates were removed from the mold.

Each of the laminates was cut into ten 12.7 mm by 254 mm tensile test coupons with a high speed diamond coated cutting blade. Two types of specimens were obtained: longitudinal (L)-containing fibers parallel and transverse (T)-containing fibers perpendicular to the tensile loading direction. 12.7 mm by 25.4 mm 6061 aluminum tabs were applied to the specimen ends. The specimens were tested for tensile properties using an Instron Model 1120 Universal Testing Machine at 4 temperatures: 25 °C, 100 °C, 175 °C, and 225 °C. Elevated temperature testing was accomplished by heating the specimens in an RI Controls radiant quad-elliptical heating furnace. The samples were equilibrated at the desired test temperature for at least 20 minutes prior to testing. Strain measurements were taken with CEA-125-UT-120 00-90° strain gauges manufactured by Measurements Group, Inc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ultimate tensile strength, tensile yield strength, and elastic modulus trends with temperature for both L and T specimens are summarized in Figs. 1 and 2. In addition, the thermal responses of monolithic 2024-T3 and 2024-T81 aluminum alloys are also plotted on these figures. The results show that in all cases, tensile strength and stiffness decrease as the test temperature increases. However, the degree of property degradation with temperature varies for each composite system. For the longitudinal ultimate tensile strength using the ambient temperature results as a baseline, PEEK/AS4 graphite and J2/Kevlar® 49 composites incorporating 2024-T81 aluminum and AF-191-M show a 9% strength reduction up to 175 °C and a 14% strength reduction for temperatures as high as 225 °C. Composite systems utilizing 2024-T3 aluminum and AF-163-2U adhesive displayed larger decreases in strength (i.e. 15% and 26% at 175 °C and 225 °C respectively). These larger decreases in tensile strength can be attributed to two factors: the reduced thermal performance of 2024-T3 aluminum as compared with 2024-T81 aluminum and the lower use temperature of AF-163-2U versus AF-191-M (150 °C versus 200 °C). For all laminates, the loss of tensile strength in the elevated temperature range was attributed to visible degradation of the adhesive system, leading to increased interlaminar delamination.

Both L and T tensile yield strengths displayed similar behavior over the test temperature range: a 3%-10% decrease up to 175 °C and a 10%-20% loss at temperatures up to 225 °C. The tensile modulus for both L and T specimens displayed the least variation with temperature. A 1%-5% decrease in stiffness was realized on heating from ambient temperature to 175 °C and only a 5%-10% drop upon heating to 225 °C. This result was attributed to the fact that if interfacial bonding was adequate, composite stiffness seemed to be dominated by the fibers which show less thermal sensitivity than the aluminum over the test temperature range.

In comparing the mechanical property data of the lamina hybrids with that measured for monolithic aluminum, the L ultimate tensile strengths are significantly superior to those of either aluminum alloy. Contrarily, the lamina hybrid strengths in the T direction are inferior to those measured for 2024-T81, but superior to 2024-T3 above 175 °C. Also, although L and T tensile yield strength and tensile modulus of the lamina hybrids are less than those for 2024-T81 aluminum, increased performance over 2024-T3 aluminum is apparent at temperatures above 175 °C.

Fig. 3 shows an optical micrograph of as processed T 2024-T81/PEEK-AS4 graphite/AF-191-M hybrid composite. The adhesive bond between the epoxy layer and both the reinforced PEEK and aluminum layers appears visually sound and free of voids. Figs. 4 and 5 are scanning electron micrographs of fractured surfaces. For longitudinal specimens, the fracture process apparently proceeded at ambient temperatures without altering the degree of constituent bonding as evidenced by Fig. 4. The adhesive layer after fracture appears to be free of cracks and virtually no fiber pullout is observed. However, these fracture characteristics change greatly at elevated temperatures above 150 °C as can be seen in Fig. 5. Both fiber pullout/fibrillation within the

thermoplastic composite layer and interfacial debonding between the lamina were commonly observed. Fiber pullout with increasing temperature was attributed to the slight softening of the polymer matrices when they are heated above their glass transition temperature (i.e. 143 °C PEEK and 145 °C J2). This softening permits the fibers an easier separation from the matrix. Interfacial debonding was attributed to visible degradation of the adhesive system at elevated temperatures. Longitudinal specimens also displayed localized fracture without the occurrence of global longitudinal splitting as previously reported by Wardle and Steenkamer [6]. Thus, the presence of the aluminum alloy appears to laterally constrain the fiber reinforced layer from splitting. For transverse specimens, matrix tensile failure and some degree of fiber splitting was ordinarily observed within the thermoplastic core region. As with the longitudinal specimens, increased interfacial debonding was commonly observed at elevated temperatures.

CONCLUSIONS

A. The aluminum/thermoplastic lamina hybrid composites retained a minimum of 75% of their ambient temperature tensile strengths, tensile yield strengths, and tensile modulus at temperatures up to 225 °C.

B. In the longitudinal direction, the ultimate tensile strengths of the aluminum-thermoplastic composite proved to be superior to either 2024-T81 or 2024-T3 monolithic aluminum alloy. However, tensile yield strength and modulus are less than those of 2024-T81, but superior to 2024-T3 at temperatures above 175 °C.

C. SEM fracturgraphy of longitudinal specimens showed that fiber pullout and interfacial debonding were the dominant fracture modes at elevated temperatures. In addition, the presence of the aluminum layer seemed to prevent multiple longitudinal fiber splitting.

D. Transverse specimen fracture was caused primarily by tensile failure within the thermoplastic matrix accompanied by some degree of fiber splitting.

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[a]

[a]

[b]

[b]

[c]

[c]

Fig. 1 Mechanical property response with temperature for longitudinal (L) lamina hybrid composites [a] tensile ultimate strength [b] tensile yield strength [c] tensile modulus

Fig. 2 Mechanical property response with temperature for transverse (T) lamina hybrid composites [a] tensile ultimate strength [b] tensile yield strength [c] tensile modulus

Fig. 3 Optical micrograph of transverse section of as processed 2024-T81/PEEK-AS4 graphite/AF 191-M hybrid displaying good adhesive bonding between the thermoplastic core and the outer aluminum sheets (100X).

Fig. 4 SEM micrograph of longitudinal ambient temperature fracture surface of 2024-T81/J2-Kevlar® 49/AF-191-M hybrid showing good interfacial bonding and minimal fiber pullout (200X).

[a]

[b]

Fig. 5 SEM micrographs demonstrating the presence of [a] fiber pullout/fibrillation (1000X) and [b] interfacial debonding commonly observed upon fracturing longitudinal (L) 2024-T81/PEEK AS4 graphite/AF-191-M samples at 225 °C.